

**“PECULIARITIES OF NEURO ORTHOPEDIC COMPLICATIONS IN CHILDREN
WITH LONG-TERM CONSEQUENCES OF CEREBRAL PALSY”**

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Annotation: *Although everyone has heard of a disease like cerebral palsy at least once, but it probably hasn't come. In general, what is cerebral palsy? The concept unites a group of chronic motor diseases resulting from damage to brain structures, and this occurs before birth, in the prenatal period. Disorders observed in an emergency can be varied. This article discusses cerebral palsy in children.*

Key words: *cerebral palsy, children, hemiplegic form, heart defects, hypertension,*

What is cerebral palsy?

Diseases of the nervous system caused by damage to the cerebral mucosa: trunk, cortex, subcortical areas, capsules. Nervous system pathology of cerebral palsy in newborns is not inherited, but some genetic factors (up to 15%) are involved in its development. To find out what the cerebral mucosa is in children, doctors can diagnose it in time and prevent the development of the disease in the perinatal period. Pathology includes various diseases: paralysis and paresis, hyperkinesia, changes in muscle tone, coordination of speech and movement, delay in motor and mental development. Traditionally, it is common to divide cerebral palsy into forms. Basic five (plus thin and unmixed):

Spastic diplegia is the most common type of pathology (40% of cases) in which the muscles of the upper or lower joints are damaged, the spine and joints are damaged.

Spastic tetraplegia, partial or complete paralysis of the arm, is one of the most severe forms, characterized by excessive muscle tension. Man cannot control his legs and arms, he suffers from pain. The hemiplegic form is characterized by muscle weakness in only half of the body. The hand on the affected side falls more to the foot. The prevalence rate is 32%. The dyskinetic (hyperkinetic) form sometimes occurs in other mucous membranes of the brain. It is expressed in the form of forced movements in the arms and legs, face and neck muscles. Ataxic is a form of cerebral palsy manifested in mitral muscle tone, ataxia (incompatibility of movements). The movements are stopped, the balance is abruptly disturbed. Children's cerebral mucosa - the causes If forms of

cerebral palsy develop, the reasons for the onset may be different. Affects fetal development during pregnancy and the first month of a baby's life. A serious risk factor is prematurity. But the root cause is not always clear. Primary migration leads to diseases such as injuries:

Intrauterine hypoxia and ischemic lesions of the fetus. Oxygen deprivation damages parts of the brain that are responsible for providing mechanical mechanisms.

Developmental disorders of brain structures.

Rhesus-prone is associated with the development of hemolytic jaundice in newborns. Pathology of pregnancy (placental abstinence, nephropathy). Sometimes, if cerebral mucosa develops, these causes are found in maternal diseases: diabetes, heart defects, hypertension, and others.

Intrauterine infections are viral, such as herpes.

Medical error at birth.

Infected and toxic damage in infants.

Symptoms of cerebral palsy

When the question arises: what is cerebral palsy, pay attention to the pathology with immediate impaired motor movement and speech. In fact, nearly a third of these diagnosed children develop other genetic diseases, such as cerebral palsy, only externally. The first signs of cerebral palsy can be detected immediately after birth. The main symptoms appear in the first 30 days:

absence of lumbar cavity and cells of eyelids;

clear asymmetry of the trunk;

muscle tone or weakness;

abnormal, slow movement of the baby;

muscle paralysis with partial paralysis;

loss of appetite, anxiety.

Later, when the child begins to actively develop, the pathology manifests itself with a lack of necessary reflexes and reactions. The toddler does not hold his head, reacts sharply to touch and does not respond to noise, performs similar movements and takes abnormal positions, does not bore his chest, shows excessive restlessness or insomnia. If you carefully monitor the development of the baby in the period up to three months, the diagnosis is true.

Stages of cerebral palsy

If a pathological diagnosis is made earlier, the chances of a complete cure are greater. The disease does not last, but it depends on the degree of brain damage. The stages of cerebral palsy in children include:

Symptoms in the first trimester;

a correlation of 4 to 3 years of age in which the initial residue (residue), pathological medium, and speech stereotypes are formed but not recorded;

an evening remnant characterized by a set of undetectable demonstrations at an early age.

Always a diagnosis of cerebral palsy guarantees disability and insolvency, but complex therapy should be started in a timely manner. The baby's brain has more opportunities to restore function. The main task of treatment in childhood is to increase the maximum level of all skills. In the initial stage, this includes the correction of motor disorders, gymnastics and massage, the stimulation of reflexes. The efforts of physicians are aimed at arresting pathologies, which can be identified by:

drugs that reduce intracranial pressure;

Stimulation of drugs for the development of CSN;

vitamin therapy;

physiotherapy.

Can brain parasites be treated?

The main question that worries the parents of a sick child is: is it possible to treat the child's cerebral mucosa? Especially when there are changes in the structure of the brain, this disease is suitable for correction. At the age of 3, 60-70% of cases can restore normal brain function and especially motor function. It is not important for the parents to miss the first symptoms so as not to ignore the appearance of abnormalities during pregnancy and childbirth.

Cerebral palsy - clinical recommendations

The primary task of physicians with a patient with cerebral palsy is not to recover to accommodate the patient. The child must realize his full potential. Treatment includes medication and other therapies, as well as training: emotional area development, hearing and speech improvement, social adjustment. Treatment with a diagnosis of infantile cerebral mucosa cannot determine the treatment. Everything depends on the complexity and localization of the lesion.

Children massage the mucous membranes of the brain

To determine what it means to start rehabilitation on time and how important it is, the child's parents should conduct regular therapeutic massage and treatment sessions with him. Daily procedures are the key to success - not only to the doctor, but also at home. Patients in the cerebral mucosa benefit greatly from massage: lymph flow and blood flow are improved, metabolism is activated, and the affected muscles are relaxed or stimulated (depending on the solution of the problem). Massage should be performed on specific muscle groups and in conjunction with breathing movements. Classic style to enjoy: Superficial and light movements of the muscle, smoothing the skin.

Shoulder muscles and hip joints skating.

Movement of large muscle groups.

Strong, adding the whole body, back and abdomen.

Characteristics of children in the cerebral mucosa

It can be difficult for parents to accept a diagnosis given to a child, but it is important not to give up and manage all efforts to rehabilitate and adapt the child. With proper care and treatment, people who are in the cerebral mucosa feel like full members of society. But it is important to understand that each pathology manifests itself in order, which determines the nature of the skin, its duration and prognosis (positive or not). The developmental characteristics of presumed children are related to the difficulties encountered in coordinating movements. This is expressed as follows: A slow movement that balances the development of thinking. There are problems with mastering math because it is difficult for children to think. Emotional disorders - weakness, vulnerability, parental attachment. He changed his mental ability. Even when the mind is developing normally and only the muscles are damaged, the child cannot break down all the incoming information as quickly as his peers. If a diagnosis of cerebral palsy is made, the prognosis of life is usually favorable. The patient may become a parent as usual and live to a very old age, but life expectancy may be reduced due to mental retardation, the development of secondary disease, and a lack of social adjustment in society in epilepsy. If you start treatment from time to time, you can achieve an almost complete recovery.

What is cerebral palsy? An unpleasant but not fatal pathology in which there is a possibility of a full life. According to statistics, 2-6 out of 1000 babies suffer from brain injury and undergo lifelong rehabilitation. Development is very complex, but the majority of patients (up to 85%) have mild to moderate disease and lead a sedentary lifestyle. Guarantee of success: Diagnosed in childhood and medical and physiotherapy, regular homework.

REFERENCE:

1. Arbashina N. A. Cerebral motor disorder. Saratov: Privolj. book publishing house, 2007.
2. Epifantseva TB Teacher-manual of the defectologist. Rostov n / D: Phoenix, 2006.
3. Children with developmental disabilities. Methodical ... pension. (Author - ND Shmatko) - M .: "Aquarium LTD", 2001. - Source: <https://muegn.ru/uz/gosty/napravleniya-raboty-s-detmi-dcp-organizaciya-raboty-s-roditelyami -detei-s-dcp.html> © muegn.ru